

ASPECTS OF DIGITAL LITERACY OF EMPLOYEES IN MATTERS OF DIGITALIZATION OF PHARMACIES

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Abstract

In modern world, where technologies play significant role in different spheres the status of healthcare professionals—medical and pharmaceutical workers—is growing due to advances in medicine and pharmacy, driven by the introduction of personalized, innovative drugs into medical practice. One of the stages of drug circulation is clinical trials, which evaluate the effectiveness and safety of interventions, including the use of drugs. This article examines the digital literacy of healthcare and pharmaceutical professionals as a key factor in the successful implementation of automation in pharmacies and other medical institutions.

Keywords: Healthcare management, pharmacy management, hospital pharmacy, digitalization of pharmacy, pharmacy optimization.

Clinical trials are conducted in medical organizations authorized to conduct them. To conduct high-quality trials in accordance with good clinical practice (GCP), medical organizations must have the necessary resources (facilities, equipment) and enough qualified medical and pharmaceutical personnel. Professional interactions between specialists are built on ethical principles as a doctrine regarding the moral value of the actions of medical and pharmaceutical workers at all levels of the healthcare system and their behavior within their field of work. Pharmaceutical ethics has much in common with medical ethics, but there are also significant differences: a pharmacist does not conduct medical examinations or prescribe medications.

The International Pharmaceutical Federation (FIP) proclaims the principle of pharmacists' collaboration with colleagues and other specialists, respecting their value systems and professional abilities. The "Ethical Code of the Russian Pharmacist" also emphasizes that "pharmacists are physicians' collaborators in administering pharmacotherapy and are also obligated to provide consultations within the limits of their competence on all properties of medicinal products, their chemical and pharmacological analogues" [1].

In the context of digitalization of healthcare, collaboration between medical and pharmaceutical workers during clinical trials is reaching the level of digital interaction. This includes not only compliance with confidentiality principles, but also communication skills via digital platforms. Effective interaction can be established by creating a unified information space in a medical organization. To achieve this, it is necessary to provide employees with computerized workstations

united into a single network, shared network resources for exchanging data and messages, communication tools, information security and other components that are common to any modern organization. Such infrastructure systems ensure uninterrupted access to data, its safety and integrity [2].

In turn, specialists must be proficient in the digital tools of automated workstations, have the skills to search and maintain electronic medical records, use medical information systems (MIS), commodity accounting systems (CAS) and other specialized services. At the same time, interaction problems may arise due to different levels of training of specialists in the field of digital technologies. It's important to consider not only the technical but also the ethical aspects of working with digital technologies [3]. One aspect of digital ethics is the right to digital literacy, which emphasizes the development of skills in using information technology.

Previous studies have identified a need for competent specialists in clinical trials. This is especially important for professional interaction in the context of the digitalization of the healthcare system [2]. However, specialists from different fields have developed uneven digital skills and abilities. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the computer literacy of medical and pharmaceutical workers to ensure the proper conduct of clinical trials, strengthen their motivation for self-development, and improve the availability of personal computers in their workplaces. Table 1 represents the level scale of personal computer proficiency what become a basis for overall general literacy.

	Level name	Level characteristic
1	Beginner (or basic)	Basic file and text manipulation skills. Ability to create, rename, copy, and move files, type text in an editor, save documents, etc.
2	Average	Proficiency in email management. Proficiency in word processing, spreadsheets, graphics editing, and product presentations (including the core elements of Microsoft Office programs).
3	Confident	Proficiency in Microsoft Office (full suite), specific software, and any browser. Ability to solve work-related problems using software.
4	Advanced	Proficiency in programming skills. Ability to troubleshoot software errors, etc.
Conducted by author based on sources [1-3]		

Based on the work of foreign scientists, six key digital competencies of healthcare workers were identified:

- 1) Information management and personal data security.
- 2) Use of digital systems and clinical safety.
- 3) Digital communication.
- 4) Information and medical knowledge management.
- 5) Patient-centeredness.
- 6) Rapid adaptation to digital innovations in healthcare [4].

Mastering digital competencies doesn't happen overnight, and this list ranks them in order of importance and relevance to daily work: First, a physician learns to work with a medical information system (MIS), gaining knowledge about how to manage patients' digital personal data and how to ensure its security. Next, they learn to use the MIS's advanced functions and conduct telemedicine consultations. However, a physician's work largely involves working with information, and the rapid accumulation of medical information over the past decade has shifted the focus from the accumulation of knowledge per se to the ability to quickly search, analyze, and synthesize new information, building on a solid foundation of basic knowledge.

Patients are increasingly demanding a more accessible and visual healthcare system. The medical community is expected to provide clear information, convenient communication, and the development and rapid implementation of digital technologies for diagnosis and treatment. Digital technologies are advancing faster than ever, and what seemed impossible just recently is becoming a reality today. Various physician decision support systems and AI-based diagnostic tools have become commonplace in clinics around the world. Those physicians who quickly and effectively implement these tools will be able to work more efficiently and effectively [5].

At the same time, we see in many countries that physicians are struggling to master digital competencies. According to the Stanford Medicine Trend Report 2020, "The Rise of the Data-Driven Physician," nearly half of physicians (47.0%) and three-quarters of medical students (73.0%) say they are seeking additional educational courses or activities to better prepare them for healthcare innovation. Meanwhile, educational programs in digital competencies, while existing, are not mandatory, and digital skills are often learned solely through personal motivation; structured and comprehensive training is rare [6].

High digital skills were defined as those healthcare workers who, according to the survey, "often" or "sometimes" use advanced HIS functions and "always" or "sometimes" use online resources during appointments. The ability to use advanced HIS functions, such as templates and samples, facilitates daily work but requires a deep understanding of the system's functionality to understand how these functions are implemented. We consider the use of online resources in daily work to be an important element of healthcare workers' digital competencies, as quickly searching and analyzing

information in the modern world is the source of accurate recommendations that healthcare workers can give to patients, and this requires the ability to use digital technologies. Low digital skills were defined as those healthcare workers who filled out the electronic medical record (EMR) with the help of colleagues or who answered "never" to the question about using online resources during appointments [7].

According to data from studies of employee competency levels in the pharmaceutical sector across countries, low digital skills are primarily found among physicians working in clinics that do not use electronic medical records (55.0%). Furthermore, such organizations typically do not provide training, as only 10.9% of physicians with low digital competencies stated that training was provided and was accessible and understandable. In other cases, training was either not provided at all or was insufficient. Furthermore, 62.7% of physicians in the cohort with low digital skills stated that their organization lacks resources for self-study that they could consult if they had questions [8].

Interestingly, in each survey group, the majority of specialists do not prescribe in the MIS and prefer to do so by hand. The response rate was 72.2% in the low-skills group, 60.9% in the medium-skills group, and 46.5% in the high-skills group. In both the higher-educated and medium- and high-skills groups, employees working in organizations that have implemented the MIS (86.9% versus 46.5% for nurses with low digital skills) possess digital skills, receive specialized training, or have access to resources that explain the workflow and are available for use if questions arise. The majority of employees with secondary vocational education, regardless of their level of digital competence, believe that using the MIS either does not affect their workflow or only partially facilitates their work (more than 50% of respondents with secondary medical education in each group) [6].

Specialists with low levels of digital competencies most often work in clinics that don't have dedicated secure consultation channels, while most highly skilled specialists, conversely, work with clinics that do. These institutions place particular emphasis on protecting patients' personal data through specialized training.

Both physicians and nurses with moderate to high digital skills mentioned that they would like to become more confident in using the MIS, including using advanced features and understanding how to correct errors generated by the system. MS Excel training was a frequent request. Physicians and nurses with high digital skills expressed a desire to learn statistical data analysis.

Physicians with moderate to high digital skills also expressed many wishes for automating routine work using the MIS, such as issuing certificates and generating accounting documentation. Physicians suggested the following ideas for reducing their routine work:

- The availability of risk calculators and clinical scales built into the MIS;
- Templates that ensure the completion of the required minimum medical documentation for a specific disease;

- Automatic uploading of test results and research data to the MIS;
- Automatic generation of specialized forms;
- Accounting of consumables for laboratories and pharmacies in the MIS;
- Integration of inpatient and outpatient data;
- Voice typing;
- Access to clinical guidelines for specific nosologies from the medical information system;
- Intuitive user interface [7-8].

Most articles on measuring digital competencies in medicine focus on studying patients, their level of digital literacy, and its impact on the course of their illnesses. Many studies emphasize the importance of developed digital competencies, although there are virtually no studies examining the competencies of healthcare workers.

The level of digital skills among healthcare workers is largely determined by the daily need for them and the organizational culture. It is lower in medical institutions that do not use a MIS and increases where both healthcare workers and management are committed to developing digital competencies. This trend applies to both doctors and nurses.

It is important to demonstrate the interdependence of a medical organization's efforts to implement a MIS and telemedicine, train staff, create conditions for high-quality and effective work, and develop digital skills in a form that can be assessed using a questionnaire. This assessment of digital competencies is subjective and surrogate, as it is impossible to conduct a true digital skills test on such a sample. It also depends on the working conditions of medical personnel, which is what we aimed to demonstrate in this article. In our study, 21% of medical workers did not have a MIS in their workplace [9]. However, we believe it is important to include them in the overall statistics, as they also have a certain level of digital competencies and a personal attitude toward digitalization.

International colleagues also agree that unlocking the full potential of eHealth is only possible when all healthcare stakeholders (healthcare workers and management) are committed to adopting and implementing information and communication technologies. Healthcare workers need motivation and a desire to gain experience with digitalization within their professional context. Colleague and organizational support appears to be an important factor in fostering a positive digitalization experience among healthcare workers. Healthcare organizations should pay attention to the social environment in the workplace and create a positive atmosphere if they want to improve their response to digitalization. Successful implementation of new technologies requires organizational and collegial support. Adopting a digital culture and developing digital skills or competencies among specialists to support digital transformation in the healthcare sector is fundamental to achieving this goal, as low digital health competence is a common perceived barrier to the adoption of eHealth services.

Researches shows that healthcare workers have a relatively high level of digital literacy in basic areas, with self-assessments of their competencies often

higher than test scores. Doctors and nurses actively use computers in their work to maintain medical records, prescribe, access patient information, search for general clinical information online, educate patients, and communicate with them, demonstrating a willingness to use digital tools in their work. Moreover, one study found no differences between doctors, students, and nursing staff.

Analysis of data collected among healthcare workers revealed that awareness, knowledge, and attitudes toward computers are generally high, but computer skills vary depending on specialty and experience.

Literary data demonstrated a correlation between computer literacy and age and education level. Young professionals and those with higher education have higher computer skills. Despite the overall high level of digital literacy, some healthcare workers reported challenges using electronic medical information resources. Therefore, it is important to provide appropriate training and education for the successful integration of eHealth. These results are consistent with our findings.

Japanese researchers have noted an interesting aspect: nurses' digital literacy in eHealth is positively correlated with active participation in hospital affairs and good collegial relationships with physicians [10].

Overall, research data confirms the importance of developing healthcare workers' digital competencies for the successful implementation and use of modern technologies in medical practice.

Therefore, to improve healthcare workers' digital competencies, it is necessary to create an environment that facilitates this development. If a clinic uses a MIS, conducts training sessions, and provides clear and easy-to-use instructions, then staff will inevitably learn to use the MIS, and over time, the tool will become convenient and user-friendly.

Medical workers with high levels of digital skills are more likely to rate the MIS as a user-friendly tool that facilitates their work, which is consistent with the results of some German studies, in which the majority of healthcare workers surveyed possessed a high level of competencies. They demonstrated a high level of trust in technology and confidence in the benefits of its use, especially among younger professionals. It's noteworthy that the group of healthcare workers with low digital competencies has the lowest percentage of those requiring the use of a MIS in their medical facilities, while the number of healthcare workers who believe the MIS hinders their work is two to four times higher in this category. This suggests that many healthcare workers are initially biased against the implementation of a MIS, but once they are trained in its full functionality, their satisfaction increases significantly.

The following components can be considered for developing the digital skills of healthcare professionals:

- implementation of the MIS within the medical institution's practice;
- mandatory, high-quality (possibly repeated) training;
- support from technical specialists at all stages;
- feedback from MIS developers to quickly correct any errors. Developers of MIS and other software

for healthcare institutions must be proactive in organizing high-quality user training on the features and capabilities of their product. Without this component, even the most well-thought-out solutions for facilitating and improving the quality of doctors' work will not be implemented, since the developers often do not recognize the low level of digital competencies of healthcare professionals.

The following point deserves special attention: doctors with high and moderate digital skills are more likely to have telemedicine consultation facilities in their clinics and have received training in personal data protection, yet they more often use instant messaging apps and email to communicate with patients. The context in which doctor-patient interactions occur requires further study, as there is a high risk of exchanging personal data over unsecured communication channels. An analysis is needed to determine whether existing telemedicine consultation systems meet the needs of both doctors and patients and whether they are user-friendly and accessible.

Digital competencies are difficult to measure because they consist of a large number of subcompetencies, and existing measurement tools are not yet able to capture this complexity. Most studies use questionnaires, but these only allow us to assess how individuals assess their competencies, which is determined not only by their personality and values, but also by their environment. This means that a physician working in a medical facility where it's common practice to fill out medical records by hand doesn't feel the need to develop their digital competencies, compared to a physician working in an innovative facility with sophisticated diagnostic equipment.

References

9. Designing a user-friendly inventory management system interface for employees with low Digital Literacy: A Design Thinking Approach. (2024). *Journal of Logistics, Informatics and Service Science*, 11(10). <https://doi.org/10.33168/jliss.2024.1003>
10. Munsour, E. E., Jaam, M., MacLure, K., & Crilly, P. (2025). The use of information and Digital Health Technologies in Medication Literacy. *Health Literacy in Medicines Use and Pharmacy*, 237–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-824407-4.00015-5>
11. Warner, B., & Gerrett, D. (2007). Reducing medication errors: Perceived information needs of healthcare practitioners. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice*, 15(3), 219–228. <https://doi.org/10.1211/ijpp.15.3.0009>
12. Maheshwari, M., Reddi, T. L., & Kela, N. (2025). Digital Health Platforms for medication management. *Technical Advances in Pharmacy: An Overview*, 193–207. <https://doi.org/10.2174/9798898812379125010011>
13. Marsh, E. (2018). Understanding the effect of digital literacy on employees' digital workplace continuance intentions and individual performance. *International Journal of Digital Literacy and Digital Competence*, 9(2), 15–33. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijdlc.2018040102>
14. Cetindamar, D., Abedin, B., & Shirahada, K. (2024). The role of employees in Digital Transformation: A preliminary study on how employees' Digital Literacy impacts use of digital technologies. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 71, 7837–7848. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tem.2021.3087724>
15. MacLure, K., & Stewart, D. (2018). A qualitative case study of ehealth and Digital Literacy Experiences of Pharmacy Staff. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 14(6), 555–563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2017.07.001>
16. Li, S., Wang, Y., & Wang, X. (2026). To embrace or to avoid: The dual path effects of digital technology requirements on employees with different digital literacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1676932>
17. Duffy, F. F., Fochtmann, L. J., Clarke, D. E., Barber, K., Hong, S.-H., Yager, J., Mościcki, E. K., & Plovnick, R. M. (2015). Psychiatrists' comfort using computers and other electronic devices in clinical practice. *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 87(3), 571–584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11126-015-9410-2>
18. Thapa, S., Nielsen, J. B., Aldahmash, A. M., Qadri, F. R., & Leppin, A. (2021). Willingness to use digital health tools in patient care among health care professionals and students at a University Hospital in Saudi Arabia: Quantitative Cross-sectional survey. *JMIR Medical Education*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.2196/18590>